

Perioperative Hyperoxygenation

for the Reduction of Surgical Site Infections in Colorectal Surgery Patients

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Background

- Surgical Site Infections (SSIs) are the **most common** type of healthcare associated infection (HAI)
- SSIs cost the US between **\$3.5-\$10 billion** annually
- 54% of SSIs** after abdominal surgery are from colorectal surgery

Current Guidelines

- WHO:** 80% FiO2 intraoperatively and 2-6 hours postop
- CDC:** Hyperoxia use intraoperatively with an ET tube

Guideline Compliance

- KPSA 2020 DNP Project Results**
 - 26 chart reviews
 - Zero** compliance by providers with recommendations

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to develop an evidence-based protocol for the use of hyperoxia, and to educate anesthesia providers on the importance of its use in the colorectal surgery patient undergoing general anesthesia with an ET tube for the prevention of SSIs.

Methods

Sample & Setting

- Kaiser Permanente West Los Angeles

Inclusion Criteria

- All employed Anesthesiologists or CRNAs

No Exclusion Criteria

Measures & Data Collection

- Protocol and module creation
- 30-day data collection
- Pretest/Posttest to assess knowledge gained
- Demographic survey

Process Measure: 50% of anesthesia providers at KPWLA complete the pretest and posttest by November 11, 2021.

Outcome Measure: 100% of the participating anesthesia providers will score at least 80% correct response on the posttest

Data Analysis and Interpretation

- 54 Anesthesia Providers** asked to participate in education module
- 1 data set removed from analysis due to lack of completion
- 18 provider results included in data analysis (32% of providers at KPWLA)**
 - 17 CRNAs**
 - 1 MDA**

Mean pretest score = **54.44 ± 21.48**

Mean posttest score = **95.56 ± 10.97**

Mean difference in score was **41.11 ± 22.20 (p <0.0001)**

Variable	Label	N	Mean	Std Dev	Median	25th Pctl	75th Pctl	Minimum	Maximum
Pretest	Pretest	18	54.44444	21.48111	60	40	60	0	80
posttest	posttest	18	95.55556	10.96638	100	100	100	60	100
diff	diff	18	41.11111	22.19933	40	20	40	20	100

- Only 21.43% of respondents were aware of the CDC and WHO guidelines**
 - 100% of providers improved on posttest
- 100% of providers agreed the module improved their knowledge**

Educational Flyer

HYPEROXIA IN COLORECTAL SURGERY

EDUCATIONAL MODULE AVAILABLE FOR ANESTHESIOLOGISTS AND CRNAs STARTING October 11- November 11, 2021.

CREATED BY KPSA SRNAs KRISTY ABEL AND CARLA MORRIS

PLEASE CONSIDER VIEWING OUR EDUCATIONAL MODULE TO ASSIST WITH OUR DOCTORATE PROJECT AND LEARN RECOMMENDED FIO2 CONCENTRATIONS IN COLORECTAL SURGICAL PATIENTS. THANK YOU!
<https://dnp.kpsan.org/login/index.php>

Discussion

Strengths

- Validated models (IOWA Model, adult learning theory)
- 100% improvement in clinician knowledge
- Study reflected current literature
- Positive feedback from staff

Weaknesses

- Data collection to determine if a change in practice has occurred following module
- Utilization of reminder tool in EMR to encourage hyperoxia use
- Use of reward system for educational modules in the future to encourage participation

Recommendations

- Creation of systemwide protocol
- EMR integration
- Incentive based learning